

Robotics – Improved Implant Outcomes and Sustainability

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Introduction

Robotics involves the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to mimic human intelligence and perform complex procedures, such as implant placement¹. Systems can be classified as robot-assisted - involving human interaction (RAIS) or fully automated (minimal human intervention).

Primary research question:

How accurate is robotic-assisted or fully automated robotic surgery in dental implant placement?

Primary Outcomes: Accuracy of implant placement.

Secondary Outcome: Patient-reported outcomes (PREMs/PROMS), economic costs, complications, and relevance to SDGs.

Inclusion Criteria

- Human clinical trials, cohort studies, case reports and randomized control trails involving dental implants placement in the maxilla/ mandible using robotics
- Studies assessing robotic surgery
- English studies

Exclusion Criteria

- Studies reporting implant placement in extra-orally harvested bone or unconventional protocols such as socket shield or trephination-based osteotomies
- In vitro or animal studies
- Articles on free-hand, s-CAIS and/or d-CAIS only

Methodology

- #1 The search was performed across, Ovid MEDLINE(R), Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL), and Embase.
 - References from databases/ registers (n= 1667)
 - Embase (n= 1079)
 - MEDLINE (n = 487)
 - CENTRAL (n= 101)
- #2 The identified articles were imported into Covidence.
 - Duplicates removed (n= 357)
- #3 Two reviewers independently assessed the eligibility of all studies – disagreements were resolved by the third author
 - Studies screened (n= 1308)
 - Studies excluded (n= 1189)
- #4 Articles that met the criteria at the abstract stage were then retrieved for full-text review.
 - Studies for retrieval (n= 118)
 - Studies excluded (n = 95)
 - Studies included (n= 23)
- #5 Risk of bias assessment
 - 20/23 studies had a low risk of bias.
- #6 Data extraction:
 - Study characteristics
 - Details on the intervention
 - Outcomes

Results

TYPES OF STUDIES

Primary Outcome:

Accuracy Metrics: Coronal deviation, apical deviation, and angular deviation on cone beam computed tomography (CBCT). These deviations assess how closely the implant is placed relative to the intended position. (Talmazov et al. metrics²)

Full Automated Robotic Implant Surgery

Type of Study	Mean Coronal Deviation	Mean Angular Deviation	Mean Apical Deviation
Case Report	0.72	1.02	0.84
Randomized Control Trail	0.78	1.76	0.92
Retrospective Cohort Study	0.53	1.31	0.59

Partial Assisted Robotic Implant Surgery

Type of Study	Mean Coronal Deviation	Mean Angular Deviation	Mean Apical Deviation
Case Report	0.53	0.79	0.56
Single Arm Clinical Trail	0.99	2.64	1.01

Secondary outcomes:

Most studies were conducted in high-income countries: China, the USA

Limited data on the economic costs. However, it noted that robotic surgery might not be as cost-effective as traditional methods.

Robotic systems can significantly contribute to SDG 3, 9, 10 and 12

Discussion

- Using Robotics has minimal deviation of implants from area of intended placement and achieved superior accuracy, particularly when compared to s-CAIS, d-CAIS and freehand implant placement.
- Full automated achieved superior results when compared to partial RAIS.
- The UN Sustainable Development Goals: 17 goals which aim to achieve peace and prosperity while tackling climate change and working towards sustainability³.
- RAIS is linked to 4 SDGs: **SDG 3:** RAIS improves accuracy, reducing postoperative complications and contributing to better overall patient outcomes, **SDG 9:** Adopting cutting-edge technology, promotes innovation in healthcare, **SDG 10:** As RAIS becomes more accessible, it has the potential to reduce health disparities by offering high-quality care in diverse settings, **SDG 12:** RAIS must consider environmental impacts such as energy consumption and material use in alignment with sustainable production practices.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

References

- Agarwal P, Nikhade P. Artificial Intelligence in Dentistry: Past, Present, and Future. Cureus. 2022 Jul 28;14(7).
- Talmazov G, Bencharit S, Waldrop TC, Ammoun R. Accuracy of implant placement position using non dental open-source software: an in vitro study. J Prosthodont. 2020;29
- The 17 goals | UN sustainable development, United Nations. Available at: <https://sdgs.un.org/goals> (Accessed: 21 October 2024).